

A comparative analysis of different respiratory motion correction approaches in free-breathing first-pass perfusion cardiac MR

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Abstract

INTRODUCTION: First-pass perfusion cardiac MR (pCMR) facilitates the non-invasive diagnosis of ischemic heart disease by capturing a sequence of images during the rapid passage of a contrast bolus through the heart¹. Traditionally, patients have been asked to hold their breath during the acquisition to minimize image degradation caused by respiratory motion. The trend of conducting acquisitions during free-breathing (FB) is growing, as it enhances reliability and provides greater comfort to the patient. In this context, the incorporation of motion correction (MoCo) approaches becomes essential for both FB acquisitions and for correcting residual motion due to insufficient breath-holding. This work evaluates the effects of different respiratory MoCo approaches in FB pCMR, both in terms of image quality and computation time.

METHODS: Data Three patients underwent a FB REST pCMR acquisition in a 1.5T scanner after written informed consent according to institutional guidelines. Acquisition parameters are: FOV=340x308 mm², in-plane resolution=2.2x2.2mm², slice thickness=10mm, 3 slices, 60 frames, TR/TE/Ts=2.1/1/100ms, $\alpha=8^\circ$, scan time=60s, contrast agent relaxivity=5.0L/mmol/s. MoCo was tested on a single short-axis slice, which was retrospectively undersampled with a 6 acceleration factor (AF), following a radial (k,t)-sampling trajectory.

Comparative analysis The following experiments were compared in the analysis:

- A compress sensing (CS) reconstruction² was performed with the NESTA algorithm without applying any MoCo.
- A CS reconstruction² after correcting the k-space with a linear phase shift (i.e., translational MoCo).
- A CS reconstruction² including in the data consistency term an elastic MoCo operator applied in the image space. Translational and elastic motion estimations (ME) were performed with pTVreg toolbox³ from both the fully-sampled sequence (i.e., I. ideal scenario) and the zero-filled sequence (i.e., II. realistic scenario).

RESULTS & DISCUSSION: Figure 1 shows the results for the three experiments and the two scenarios for a representative patient. In the ideal scenario (I), in which we have the fully-sampled sequence to perform accurate ME, the MoCo was clearly higher in experiment c). However, when the ME is performed from the zero-filled sequence (II), differences between b) and c) decrease, which is presumably caused by a less accurate elastic ME. Overall, experiments b) and c) obtained better results compared to not applying any MoCo. In terms of computation time, experiments a) and b) are equivalent, but the computation time surges when the elastic MoCo operator is included in the reconstruction (~x4 reconstruction time).

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Figure 1 – Comparative results for both scenarios (i.e., I. ideal and II. realistic) and experiments a) CS without MoCO, b) CS with previously translational k-space MoCo and c) CS including elastic MoCo operator in image space. Imaging results are shown over 2 different frames. For each experiment reconstruction times are reported. Temporal intensity profiles are shown in x-t and y-t directions as indicated by horizontal (green) and vertical (blue) dashed lines.

References

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